

$n + 1$ -Parameter singular fractional differential equation

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Abstract: In this paper, we will study the nonlinear Langevin equation that includes $n + 1$ fractional order $0 < \alpha_i \leq 1, i = \overline{1, n + 1}$ and some terms. According to Banach’s contraction theorem and Krasnoselski’s fixed point theorem, we obtain the results of the existence and uniqueness of the solutions. With some examples.

Key words: Nonlinear Langevin equation; Caputo derivative; Existence of solution; Fixed point.

1. Introduction

In this paragraph, we know the Langevin equation, first formulated by Langevin in 1908 as an effective tool to describe the evolution of physical phenomena in volatile environments [2, 7]. The general form of nonlinear Langevin fractional equations As:

$${}^c\mathcal{D}^{\alpha} {}^c\mathcal{D}^{\beta} u(t) + \delta {}^c\mathcal{D}^{\alpha} u(t) = h(t, u(t))$$

${}^c\mathcal{D}^{\alpha}$, ${}^c\mathcal{D}^{\beta}$ are the Caputo’s fractional derivatives of orders $m - 1 \leq \alpha \leq m, n - 1 \leq \beta < 1, n, m \in \mathbb{N}$, and $h : [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuously differentiable function, [13].

S. Kosari, M. Yadollahzadeh, Z. Shao, and Y. Rao [6] investigated the existence and uniqueness of solutions a generalization of the nonlinear Langevin equation of different fractional orders with four-point boundary conditions provided as:

$$\begin{cases} {}^c\mathcal{D}_{0+}^{\beta} ({}^c\mathcal{D}_{0+}^{\alpha} + \mu) u(t) = g(t, u(t), u'(t)), t \in (0, 1), \\ u(0) = u(1) = u'(0) = u'(1) = 0, 0 < \alpha, \beta \leq 1, 2 < \beta \leq 3 \end{cases}$$

where ${}^c\mathcal{D}^{\alpha}$ is the Caputo fractional derivative of order α , $g : [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function and μ is a real number.

In this work we study the existence, uniqueness of solutions a generalization from the nonlinear Langevin

equation involving $(n + 1)$ fractures that includes the arrangement of Caputo fractional-order of the form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_1} ({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_2} (\dots {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_n} ({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} + \delta) \dots)) u(t) = h(t, u(t)), t \in [0, 1] \\ u(a) = 0, \\ {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(a) = 0, \\ {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_n} ({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(a)) = 0, \\ \vdots \\ {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_3} (\dots ({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_n} ({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(a)))) = 0, \\ {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_2} ({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_3} (\dots {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_n} ({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} + \delta) \dots)) u(b) = 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

where ${}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_i}, i = \overline{1, n+1}$ are the Caputo fractional derivative of orders $\alpha_i, 1 \leq \sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i \leq 2$, and

$\delta > 0$, to be defined later, $h : [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a given function satisfying some assumptions that will be specified later,

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we introduce some notations and definitions of fractional calculus and present preliminary results needed in our proofs later. We are indebted to the terminologies used in the books,

Definition 2.1. ([1]). For $q > 0$, the left-sided Riemann Liouville fractional integral of order q for an integrable function $u : J \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$$\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^q u(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(q)} \int_a^t (t-s)^{q-1} u(s) ds, \quad (2)$$

where Γ is the gamma function.

Definition 2.2. ([3, 10]) Let $n \in \mathbb{Z}_+^*$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_+^*$ such that $n-1 < \alpha \leq n$. The left-sided Caputo fractional derivative of a function $h : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$${}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^\alpha h(t) = \int_0^t \frac{(t-s)^{n-\alpha-1}}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} f^{(n)}(s) ds.$$

Lemma 2.1. ([3, 10]) Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $n-1 < \alpha \leq n$. If x is a continuous function, then we have

$$\mathcal{I}^{\alpha c} \mathcal{D}^\alpha x(t) = x(t) + c_0 + c_1 t + \dots + c_{n-1} t^{n-1}.$$

Lemma 2.2. ([1]) Let $q, p > 0$, and $u \in L^1(J)$. Then

$$\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^q \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^p u(t) = \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{q+p} u(t), \quad t \in J.$$

In particular,

If $u \in C(J)$. Then $\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^q \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^p u(t) = \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{q+p} u(t), t \in J$.

Lemma 2.3. ([10]) Let $q > 0, n \in \mathbb{N}$; such that $n-1 < p \leq n$. Then:

- ${}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^p \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^q u(t) = {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{p-q} u(t)$; if $p > q$.
- ${}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^p \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^q u(t) = \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{q-p} u(t)$; if $q > p$.

Lemma 2.4. ([11]) Given a function $u \in C^n [a, b]$ and $0 < q < 1$, we have

$$|\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^q u(z) - \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^q u(s)| \leq \frac{2(z-s)^q}{\Gamma(q+1)} \|u\|.$$

Lemma 2.5. If $h \in C [0, 1]$, then the boundary value problem (1) has unique solution is given by

$$u(t) = \left(\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i} \right) h(t) - \left(\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i} \right) h(1) - \delta \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(t).$$

Proof.

□

We use the property established in Lemma 2.1 and Lemma 2.2 to (1), we find that

$${}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_1} ({}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_2} (\dots {}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_n} ({}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} + \delta) \dots)) u(t) = h(t),$$

so

$$\begin{aligned} u(t) &= \left(\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i} \right) h(t) - \delta \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(t) \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=2}^n \left(\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\sum_{1 \leq i \leq j+1} \alpha_i} \right) c_{j-1} + \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} c_{n-1} + c_n \end{aligned}$$

Some of the initial conditions allow us to write:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} u(a) = 0 \implies c_n = 0 \\ \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(a) = 0 \implies c_{n-1} = 0 \\ {}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_n} ({}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(a)) = 0 \implies c_{n-2} = 0 \\ {}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n-1}} ({}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_n} ({}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(a))) = 0 \implies c_{n-2} = 0 \\ \vdots \\ {}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_3} (\dots ({}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n-1}} ({}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_n} ({}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(a)))) = 0 \implies c_2 = 0 \\ {}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_2} ({}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_3} (\dots {}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_n} ({}^c \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} + \delta) \dots)) u(b) = 0 \implies c_1 = -\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\alpha_1} h(b) \end{array} \right.$$

so

$$u(t) = \left(\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i} \right) h(t) - \left(\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i} \right) h(1) - \delta \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(t)$$

3. Existence of solution

Let $\mathbb{E} = C([a, b], \mathbb{R})$ the Banach space. For all continuous functions of $[a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ has the norm defined as

$$\|u(t)\| = \sup \{u(t), t \in [a, b]\}.$$

For the convenience, we set

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{M} &= \frac{2(b-a)^{1+\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i}}{\Gamma\left(\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i + 1\right)} \\ \mathcal{N} &= \frac{\delta(b-a)^{\alpha_{n+1}}}{\Gamma(\alpha_{n+1} + 1)} < 1,\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

We define the operator $\mathbb{L} : \mathbb{E} \rightarrow \mathbb{E}$ by

$$(\mathbb{L}u)(t) = \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1+\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i} h_u(t) - \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1+\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i} h_u(1) - \delta \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(t)\tag{4}$$

where

$$h_u(t) = h(t, u(t))$$

The problem (1) has solutions in the case of the operator (4) containing fixed points.

Theorem 3.1. *Let $h : [a, b] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ it is a continuous joint function that fulfills the condition*

$$|h(t, u) - h(t, v)| \leq \mathcal{K} |u - v|,$$

where \mathcal{K} is the Lipschitz constant. Then the boundary value problem (1) has a unique solution if $\frac{\mathcal{M}}{1-\mathcal{N}} < \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}}$, where \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} is given by (3).

Proof. In the first step, for \mathbb{L} defined in(4), We explain that $\mathbb{L}\mathbb{B}_r \subset \mathbb{B}_r$, where $\mathbb{B}_r = \{u \in \mathbb{E} : \|u\| \leq r\}$. For that, set $\sup_{t \in [a, b]} |h_0(t)| = \rho$ (where $h_0(t) = h(t, 0)$) and choose $r \geq \frac{\rho \mathcal{M}}{1-(\mathcal{M}\mathcal{K} + \mathcal{N})}$, where \mathcal{M} defined in(3). For

$u \in \mathbb{B}_r$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\mathbb{L}u\| &= \sup_{t \in [a,b]} |(\mathbb{L}u)(t)| \\
 &= \sup_{t \in [a,b]} \left| \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i} h_u(t) + \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i} h_u(1) + \delta \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(t) \right| \\
 &\leq \sup_{t \in [a,b]} \left(\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i} \right) (|(h_u - h_0)(t)| + |h_0(t)|) \\
 &\quad + \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i} (|(h_u - h_0)(1)| + |h_0(1)|) + \delta \sup_{t \in [a,b]} \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} |u(t)| \\
 &\leq \sup_{t \in [a,b]} \left(\mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i} \right) (\mathcal{K}|u| + \rho) \\
 &\quad + \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i} (\mathcal{K}|u| + \rho) + \frac{\delta(b-a)^{\alpha_{n+1}}}{\Gamma(\alpha_{n+1} + 1)} r \\
 &\leq \frac{2(b-a)^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i}}{\Gamma \left(\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i + 1 \right)} (\mathcal{K}r + \rho) + \frac{\delta(b-a)^{\alpha_{n+1}}}{\Gamma(\alpha_{n+1} + 1)} r \\
 &\leq r
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, let $u, v \in \mathbb{E}$ for each $t \in [a, b]$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\mathbb{L}u - \mathbb{L}v\| &= \sup_{t \in [a,b]} |(\mathbb{L}u - \mathbb{L}v)(t)| \\
 &= \sup_{t \in [0,1]} \left| \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i} (h_u - h_v)(t) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i} (h_u - h_u)(1) + \delta \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} (u - v)(t) \right| \\
 &\leq \sup_{t \in [0,1]} \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i} (\mathcal{K}|(u - v)(t)|) \\
 &\quad + \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1 \sum \alpha_i} (\mathcal{K}|(u - v)(t)|) + \delta \sup_{t \in [0,1]} \mathcal{I}_{a^+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} |(u - v)(t)| \\
 &\leq (\mathcal{K}\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}) \|u - v\|
 \end{aligned}$$

According to $\mathcal{K} < \frac{1-\mathcal{N}}{\mathcal{M}}$, then \mathbb{L} is a contraction. The conclusion of the theorem of the contraction mapping principle. Ends the proof. \square

We study existence of solutions for problem (1) by using Krasnoselski's fixed point theory.

Theorem 3.2. ([12]). Let \mathbb{T}_1 and \mathbb{T}_2 be two operators and Ω be a closed convex and nonempty subset of Banach space \mathbb{E} . Such that: 1. $\mathbb{T}_1x + \mathbb{T}_2x \in \Omega$

2. \mathbb{T}_1 is continuous and compact;

3. \mathbb{T}_2 is a contraction mapping.

Then there exists $x \in \Omega$ such that $x = \mathbb{T}_1 x + \mathbb{T}_2 x \in \Omega$

Theorem 3.3. Assume that $h : [a, b] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a jointly continuous function and the following assumptions hold:

\mathcal{H}_1) $|h(t, u) - h(t, v)| \leq \mathcal{K} |u - v|, \forall t \in [a, b], u, v \in \mathbb{R}$;

\mathcal{H}_2) $|h(t, u)| \leq w(t)$ for all $(t, u) \in [a, b] \times \mathbb{R}$ with $w \in C[a, b]$.

Then the boundary value problem (1) has at least one solution in $[a, b]$ if $\frac{\mathcal{M}}{2} < \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}}$.

Proof. Set $\sup_{t \in [a, b]} |w(t)| \leq \|w\|$ and consider $\mathbb{B}_r = \{u \in \mathbb{E} : \|u\| \leq r\}$ with fix

$$r \geq \frac{\mathcal{M} \|w\|}{2(1 - \mathcal{N})},$$

define the two operators \mathbb{L}_1 and \mathbb{L}_2 on \mathbb{B}_r as

$$(\mathbb{L}_1 u)(t) = \mathcal{I}_{0+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \sum^{\alpha_i} h_u(t)$$

and

$$(\mathbb{L}_2 u)(t) = -\mathcal{I}_{0+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \sum^{\alpha_i} h_u(1) - \delta \mathcal{I}_{a+}^{\alpha_{n+1}} u(t)$$

For $u, v \in \mathbb{B}_r$, it follows from (4) that

$$\|\mathbb{L}_1 u + \mathbb{L}_2 v\| \leq \mathcal{M} \|w\| + \mathcal{N} r \leq r.$$

Therefore, $\mathbb{L}_1 u + \mathbb{L}_2 v \in \mathbb{B}_r$. According to $\frac{\mathcal{M}}{2} < \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}}$ it can be shown that \mathbb{L}_2 is a contraction mapping. The continuity of the operator \mathbb{L}_1 extracted from the continuity of the function h . Also, \mathbb{L}_1 is uniformly bounded on \mathbb{B}_r as

$$\|(\mathbb{L}_1 u)(t)\| \leq \frac{\mathcal{M} \|w\|}{2},$$

In order to prove the compactness of the operator \mathbb{L}_1 , suppose that $\mathbb{D} = [a, b] \times \mathbb{B}_r \subset \mathbb{E}$. Thus, for all $u \in \mathbb{B}_r$ and $t_1, t_2 \in [a, b]$ with $a \leq t_1 < t_2 \leq b$

$$\begin{aligned} \|(\mathbb{L}_1 u)(t_2) - (\mathbb{L}_1 u)(t_1)\| &= \sup_{t \in [a, b]} |(\mathbb{L}_1 u)(t_2) - (\mathbb{L}_1 u)(t_1)| \\ &= \sup_{t \in [a, b]} \left| \mathcal{I}_{a+}^{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \sum^{\alpha_i} (h_u(t_1) - h_u(t_2)) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{(b-a)^{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \sum^{\alpha_i}}{\Gamma \left(\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n+1} \alpha_i + 1 \right)} (t_2 - t_1)^{\alpha_{n+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

Which is independent of u and approaches zero when letting $t_2 \rightarrow t_1$. Thus, \mathbb{L}_1 is relatively compact on \mathbb{B}_r . Hence by the Arzela-Ascoli Theorem, the operator \mathbb{L}_1 is compact on. Thus all assumptions of Theorem 3.3

are satisfied and the conclusion of Theorem 3.2 implies that the boundary value problem (1) has at least one solution in $[a, b]$. This completes the proof. \square

Example 3.1. Consider the boundary value problem

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\frac{1}{4}} \left({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\frac{1}{4}} \left({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \right) \right) \right) u(t) = h(t, u), t \in [a, b] = [1, 2] \\ u(1) = 0, \\ {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\frac{1}{2}} u(1) = 0, \\ {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\frac{1}{4}} \left({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\frac{1}{2}; \psi} u(1) \right) = 0, \\ {}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\frac{1}{4}} \left({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\frac{1}{4}} \left({}^c\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \right) \right) u(2) = 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} h(t, u) &= t^2 + \frac{1}{1 + |u|}. \\ w(t) &= t^3 + \frac{1}{2} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\mathcal{M} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{N} = \frac{1}{\pi} < 1.$$

By Theorem 3.1 that problem (5) has a unique solution. Thus, by Theorem 3.2 the boundary value problem (5) has a unique solution on $[0, 1]$.

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